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Clustering Event I

Co-production of Policy Recommendations - Bridging Physics and Biology & Ecosystem Ocean Science

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the outcomes of the first clustering event jointly organised by the Horizon Europe projects BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim, aimed at advancing ocean observation strategies through the co-production of policy recommendations. The report addresses critical challenges in current ocean observing systems and monitoring frameworks, emphasising the need for a more integrated, standardised, and interdisciplinary approach to observing physical, biogeochemical, and biological components of the ocean system.

A core focus is the systematic implementation and operationalisation of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), managed by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS). EOVs provide a globally recognised framework for harmonising observations across disciplines and supporting evidence-based policy development. While EOVs for physical and biogeochemical variables are relatively mature, biological and ecosystem EOVs remain underrepresented, limiting the capacity to assess climate-driven changes in marine ecosystems and constraining biodiversity conservation strategies.

The clustering event convened about 25 partner organizations across Europe, representing over 30 international initiatives and projects, to identify barriers and propose solutions to strengthen global ocean observing systems. Key issues addressed include fragmented observation efforts, data integration challenges across spatial and temporal scales, and the lack of standardised methodologies, particularly regarding biological observations. Bridging Land, Coastal, and Ocean Observing Systems was one focus during the event. Marine Heatwaves (MHWs) were used as a central case, both during the event and beyond to illustrate the complex interactions between physics and biology & ecosystem impacts, highlighting the need for coordinated and comprehensive observation strategies.

In response to these challenges, the report advocates for an integrated suite of policy recommendations. It calls for expanding the application of EOVs, particularly by advancing the integration of biological and ecosystem variables alongside physical and biogeochemical data. It promotes upgrading and diversifying observation platforms, enhancing the linkage between satellite and in situ systems, and addressing scale mismatches, applying downscaling methodologies that can translate global datasets into regionally actionable insights. The report emphasises the need to harmonise data collection protocols under FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles to facilitate data sharing and meta-analyses, and highlights the potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and advanced data analytics to overcome current observational constraints and improve forecasting capabilities.

Furthermore, it stresses the importance of enhancing interdisciplinary collaboration and capacity building, through regular workshops and stakeholder engagement, as essential mechanisms for ensuring that scientific insights are effectively translated into policy measures. Ultimately, the report underscores that by adopting an integrated, multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary, and transdisciplinary approach to ocean observation and data integration, policymakers can significantly improve marine conservation strategies,

strengthen climate resilience, and contribute to the sustainable management of ocean resources. These actions directly align with key European policy objectives, including the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters, the European Green Deal, and the development of a Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO), while supporting broader international environmental frameworks and global socio-economic stability.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMOC	Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
EMODnet	Copernicus Marine Service and European Marine Observation and Data Network
EMSO	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water-column Observatory
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
MHWs	Marine Heatwaves
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
SDGs	UN Sustainable Development Goals
SST	Sea surface temperature
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species

1. Introduction

The global ocean plays a fundamental role in climate regulation, biodiversity maintenance and global socio-economic stability (Muller-Karger et al., 2024; Visbeck, 2018). However, anthropogenic pressures, including climate change, pollution, and habitat degradation, have significantly altered oceanic processes and states. Therefore, stronger collaboration across disciplines and robust multidisciplinary monitoring frameworks to assess changes in marine systems are required (e.g., Levin et al., 2019; Miloslavich et al., 2024). To meet this challenge, ocean research must be increasingly multi-, inter- and transdisciplinary, combining expertise across domains to develop and advance our understanding of the ocean.

Furthermore, there is a need to develop and operationalise Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) which provide a standardised framework for observing and understanding the ocean system, encompassing physical variables (e.g., temperature, salinity), biogeochemical variables (e.g., Dissolved Oxygen, Particulate Organic Matter), and biology & ecosystems variables (e.g., species composition, biomass, habitat areal extent). EOVs span physics, biogeochemistry and biology & ecosystems and are managed by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) programme (Figure 1). Each EOV has a specification sheet, basically a recipe with recommendations on what and how to measure and how to ensure the data follows Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) data principles. GOOS EOVs are developed to deliver ocean forecasts and early warnings, climate projections and assessments to protect ocean health and its benefits.

Despite advancements in ocean observing networks, gaps remain, particularly regarding biology & ecosystem EOVs which are currently largely absent from global ocean observation frameworks (Miloslavich et al., 2018; Sloyan et al., 2019; Tanhua et al., 2019a). This knowledge gap limits our capacity to evaluate the effects of climate change on marine ecosystems and constrains the formulation of effective biodiversity conservation strategies. It underscores the urgent need to integrate biological and ecological insights into global ocean observation systems, especially as policymakers strive to develop comprehensive frameworks that account for both environmental shifts and their ecological implications (Gissi et al., 2019). Standardized global ocean variables and a standardised ocean indicator framework that incorporates biological insights could enhance decision-making processes for marine conservation and climate mitigation strategies (Miloslavich et al., 2024).

To improve collaboration and address the critical gap in physics and biology & ecosystem integration, ObsSea4Clim and BioEcoOcean held a joint clustering event. This timely initiative responded to the growing need for cross-sectoral coordination, promoting collaboration across disciplines in ocean science and policy. The goal was to co-develop solutions to improve EOV-based global ocean monitoring, with an emphasis on linking physical and biology & ecosystem data. By driving interdisciplinary cooperation, this effort aims to deliver practical recommendations for policymakers and support more effective and integrated ocean governance.

Figure 1. Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) span physics, biogeochemistry and biology & ecosystems and are managed by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) programme, and three expert panels respectively. The majority of EOVs are also Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) defined by the Global Climate Observing System. Figure source: Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS).

1.1 EOVs and their role in policy development

By enabling systematic data collection and integration, EOVs form the scientific backbone for evidence-based decision-making in marine governance. They contribute to international environmental agreements (e.g., SDG 14, the Paris Agreement, Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework), regional strategies such as the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and operational programs including Copernicus Marine Service and European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet).

Furthermore, EOVs allow the harmonisation of observations across disciplines, enabling multidisciplinary data assimilation into climate, ecosystem and socio-economic models (Sloyan et al., 2019). These models can then feed into marine spatial planning, risk assessment, early warning systems, and policy performance evaluation. Despite the established utility of EOVs, challenges persist due to the lack of standardised methodologies across projects and regions, fragmented data collection among disciplines, and limited integration of biological and ecosystem variables into forecasting systems. Despite the importance of biodiversity monitoring, there is a gap in the development and implementation of biological EOV indicators. Studies highlight that EOVs enhance predictive modelling and improve early warning systems by integrating remote sensing and in situ observations (Rolle et al., 2023). EOVs are also essential for detecting anomalies linked to marine heatwaves (MHWs) (Brando et al., 2024). The integration of these datasets enables

assessment of the ecological and socio-economic impacts of MHWs. Recognising these gaps, the clustering event sought to foster cross-disciplinary alignment and initiate a shared strategy for EOVS operationalisation in policy-relevant contexts.

These cross-disciplinary and bridging efforts are particularly aligned with the strategic priorities of Horizon Europe, including the development of a Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) and the overarching objectives of the European Green Deal. Both frameworks emphasise the urgent need for sustainable marine resource management, enhanced biodiversity conservation, and climate resilience. Within this context, Horizon Europe highlights the critical importance of advancing ocean observation capabilities to support climate adaptation strategies, reinforce ecosystem resilience, improve methodologies for ocean-based carbon sequestration monitoring, and enhance the tracking of marine biodiversity. Similarly, the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters aims to restore marine ecosystems, eradicate pollution, and foster a sustainable blue economy, all of which are fundamentally underpinned by robust and integrated ocean monitoring systems.

Strengthening the use and application of biology & ecosystem EOVS as well as promoting integration between physics and biology & ecosystem EOVS is instrumental in achieving these objectives. Enhanced EOVS-based frameworks contribute to more precise and comprehensive data collection on marine pollution, fisheries sustainability, and the health of marine ecosystems. These improvements enable evidence-based policy development, support marine spatial planning, and foster cross-sectoral collaboration for ocean governance. Furthermore, the objectives of EOVS development are closely aligned with the mission of BioEcoOcean, dedicated to improving marine biodiversity assessments, promoting integrated ocean governance, and strengthening the science-policy interface. By addressing critical gaps in biology & ecosystem EOVS and their integration with physics EOVS, this clustering event reinforces BioEcoOcean's overarching aim to bridge the disconnect between ocean science and policy-making.

1.2 The Need for a Co-Design and Co-Production Approach

Effectively translating ocean observations into actionable outcomes requires adopting a co-design and co-production framework characterised by cross-sectoral coordination and interdisciplinary collaboration. The co-design approach delivers a comprehensive and interconnected understanding of marine environments by integrating physical, biogeochemical, and biology & ecosystem data. This interdisciplinary integration significantly enhances the relevance of scientific findings, addresses societal needs, and strengthens ocean governance. It aligns scientific research with societal priorities, fosters increased stakeholder engagement, and facilitates the incorporation of scientific insights into policymaking. Additionally, active engagement across disciplines encourages mutual learning and knowledge exchange, enriching scientific inquiry and decision-making processes through diverse expertise. This approach has been successfully demonstrated by international initiatives such as the [GEO Blue Planet](#), which uses oceanographic data for societal applications, including early warning systems and sustainable fisheries management.

Strategically coordinated events and collaborations have highlighted the value of interdisciplinary partnerships. These efforts improved measurement standardisation, data interoperability, and established

clear priorities for global ocean monitoring through EOVs, as shown by initiatives like the GOOS and the European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water-column Observatory (EMSO) (Moltmann et al., 2019; EMSO, 2021). Such coordination helps develop clear, actionable recommendations to strengthen global ocean governance.

The following chapters will explore policy recommendations developed through collaboration between the EU-funded Horizon Europe projects, BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4clim (read more about the projects in 3.2). Firstly, we will demonstrate the importance of bridging physics and biology & ecosystems using case studies to illustrate how MHWs affect key biological and ecological components, emphasising critical EOv sub-variables essential for comprehensive monitoring. Furthermore, the chapters will evaluate the socio-economic consequences of MHWs, highlighting their effects on human activities and coastal communities. Through continued collaboration and targeted innovation, ocean monitoring frameworks can effectively respond to MHWs, becoming increasingly adaptive, resilient, and closely aligned with scientific objectives and societal needs. Secondly, we will take a deep dive into the blue frontier by describing the exciting content and outcome of the clustering event held by the two projects BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim. This includes discussions combining physics and biology & ecosystem EOvs, bridging land, coast and open ocean, the importance of scale in MHWs on ecologically relevant scales and key issues and barriers in ocean observing. Lastly, we will provide co-developed policy recommendations.

2. Bridging Physics and Biology & Ecosystem Ocean Science - Exemplified by marine heatwaves and their impacts on marine life

Marine heatwaves (MHWs) — extended periods of anomalously high ocean temperatures lasting from days to months — are increasingly recognised as major stressors in marine ecosystems. These events can span local coastal areas or entire ocean basins and have been linked to a wide array of biological disruptions, including mass mortalities, coral bleaching, fishery collapses, and aquaculture failures. Understanding MHWs is, therefore, not only a matter of physical oceanography but also of urgent ecological importance.

MHWs are typically identified through satellite-derived sea surface temperature (SST) data, which allow broad spatial coverage and long-term trend analysis. However, many of the most severe ecological impacts occur below the surface, particularly in coastal regions where biological productivity is highest. Capturing the subsurface evolution of MHWs remains a major challenge due to the limited availability of in-situ observations. The complexity of nearshore dynamics, including stratification and local hydrodynamics, means that surface measurements alone often underestimate the full extent of thermal anomalies. Some well-known examples include the “Blob” (2013–2016) in the northeast Pacific, which triggered wide-ranging ecosystem changes along the west coast of North America, and recurrent heatwaves in the Great Barrier Reef that cause catastrophic coral bleaching. These events underscore the need for better vertical resolution in temperature monitoring, especially in biologically sensitive areas.

To fully understand the impacts of MHWs, it is essential to integrate biological and ecosystem data alongside physical measurements. Temperature anomalies do not act in isolation — they intersect with

biological systems in complex, often non-linear ways. Organisms respond to heat stress through altered physiology, reduced reproductive success, and increased mortality. At the community and ecosystem level, MHWs can trigger cascading effects such as:

- Disruption of food webs, as species at different trophic levels respond unequally.
- Habitat loss, including coral bleaching and the collapse of kelp forests.
- Range shifts and biodiversity loss, altering ecosystem structure and function.

Such responses are not captured by SST data alone. They require ecological time series, species distribution records, physiological data, and biodiversity monitoring, often collected through long-term ecological observatories and integrated observing systems.

Bridging the gap between physics and biology demands more comprehensive coastal monitoring strategies. Deploying high-resolution in-situ systems — such as moored observatories, coastal Argo floats, gliders, animal-borne sensors, and autonomous platforms — is critical for capturing both the vertical structure of thermal anomalies and the biological responses they provoke. These platforms can also carry sensors to monitor oxygen, chlorophyll, turbidity, and other key biogeochemical and ecological variables. A truly integrated observing approach — one that aligns physical, biological, and ecosystem data — will enhance our capacity to detect, understand, and predict the impacts of MHWs in a changing climate. Such integration is essential for supporting ecosystem-based management, informing marine spatial planning, and safeguarding ocean biodiversity.

2.1 Socio-economic impact of MHWs in relation to biology & ecosystems

MHWs can change the functions of ecosystems and reduce the provision of ecosystem services, including loss of benefits, especially in fisheries and aquaculture, as well as damage to habitat functions due to the loss of important organisms such as corals, kelp and seagrasses (Smith et al., 2021). Population declines and low recruitment of commercially important species resulting from MHWs can cause reductions in fishing quotas and even closure of fisheries. For example, a MHW in the Mediterranean Sea in 1999 led to mass mortalities of benthic organisms, reduced growth and reproduction, as well as coral bleaching, which led further to revenue losses from tourism. Cultural ecosystem services suffer from mass extinctions of charismatic species such as marine mammals, seabirds, and corals, and regulating ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration and nutrient cycles are affected.

The average estimated direct economic loss from a single MHW event is estimated to exceed USD 800 million, while indirect losses due to impaired ecosystem services can surpass USD 3.1 billion annually (Smith et al., 2021). The loss of seagrass meadows in Shark Bay, Western Australia, after a MHW in 2011, was estimated to be a loss of ecosystem services worth USD 3.1 billion per year (Strydom et al., 2020). Loss estimates, like in the case of a 2018 MHW in the Baltic and North Seas causing kelp forest losses, are not always feasible. The actual costs related to MHWs are likely higher as many socio-economic effects remain undetected or not notified, especially in low-income countries. Nevertheless, MHWs can also result in short-term socio-economic opportunities, for instance, increased tourism or improved fishing prospects.

The impacts of MHWs are linked to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), in the fight against hunger (SDG 2), the promotion of decent work and economic growth (SDG 8), and the protection of life underwater (SDG 14) (FAO, 2010). Disturbances in fisheries and aquaculture by MHWs can endanger food security and the livelihoods of coastal communities. Adaptation and mitigation measures are, therefore, urgently needed to reduce the risks and consequences of interactions between humans and coasts/oceans/seas. These include improved climate forecasts, proactive resource management, and strengthening the resilience of marine ecosystems. In addition, a more informed understanding of the cumulative effects of MHWs and other anthropogenic stressors is necessary (Smith et al., 2021).

2.2 Case studies of effects of MHWs on biology & ecosystems

This section presents case studies from project partners, and project friends, illustrating the diverse impacts of MHWs on ecosystems and species. MHWs can trigger habitat degradation, species shifts, food web disruptions, and losses in key ecosystem services such as fisheries and carbon sequestration, with significant socio-economic consequences.

The selected case studies highlight regional and taxonomic differences in MHW effects, from seagrass loss in the Mediterranean to zooplankton tipping points in the Arctic to pyrosome blooms in the Northeast Pacific (Figure 2). These examples underscore the complexity of MHW impacts and the need for improved monitoring, predictive models, and adaptive management strategies. By exemplifying MHW and their effect on biology & ecosystems we are working towards providing policy-relevant recommendations to enhance resilience to MHWs.

Figure 2. Overview of marine ecosystem case studies showcasing the diversity of biological communities in different settings including seagrass meadows, macroalgae-dominated habitats, structurally complex kelp forests, bioluminescent pyrosome colonies), and dynamic zooplankton populations. Each case study highlights unique ecological roles and environmental interactions critical to sustaining ocean health.

2.2.1 Seagrass Under Siege: MHWs, Algal Blooms, and Coastal Decline

MHWs indirectly impact coastal ecosystems like macroalgae and seagrass. They cause a sudden rise in water temperature, triggering eutrophication events. Combined with pollution, this leads to rapid growth of free-floating mucilaginous algae, which can submerge and cover the seabed when their volumes become large and heavy (Figure 3). This results in the seagrass meadow being covered by the algae, reducing their capability for photosynthesis. As seagrasses are marine flowering plants, a prolonged occurrence of this phenomenon can lead to necrosis across vast areas of the seagrass meadows. The consequences are significant for the food webs and the local economies, as the fish stocks may collapse since only limited food resources and shelter are available for the species dependent on the seagrass meadows (Benedetti-Cecchi 2024). Consequently, the local fishers will experience significant loss in their fish catches and their income. The local tourism sector will also suffer, since seagrasses support water clarity and purification from pathogens (Nordlund et al., 2016). In addition, diving and snorkelling sites will be lost, as these will also be completely covered by the mucilaginous algae.

Figure 3. Healthy *Posidonia* seagrass meadow (far left) vs Impact of mucilaginous algae on *Posidonia* seagrass meadows (middle, and far right a close-up). Photos by Dimitris Poursanidis, C-BLUES, shot in National Marine Park of Alonissos Northern Sporades, Greece, during summer 2019.

2.2.2 Biodiverse macroalgal forests at risk

Macroalgal forests, dominated by canopy-forming kelps (Laminariales) and fucoids (Fucales), are iconic components of temperate and subpolar rocky reef ecosystems worldwide (Fragkopoulou et al., 2022). These structurally complex habitats support high levels of biodiversity, regulate nutrient and energy flows, and contribute significantly to carbon cycling and long-term sequestration (Krause-Jensen and Duarte 2016). They also provide a wide range of key ecosystem services, including nursery habitats for commercially important species (e.g., fish, crustaceans, molluscs), buffering of coastal erosion through wave attenuation, and support tourism and coastal livelihoods (Filbee-Dexter and Wernberg, 2018).

Macroalgal forests are increasingly threatened by a combination of global and local stressors. Abrupt declines in canopy-forming species occur in response to intensifying MHWs (Smale et al., 2019). The effects of climate change cumulate with chronic anthropogenic pressures such as overgrazing, eutrophication, invasive species, and altered disturbance regimes contributing to long-term structural degradation and

shifts to alternative habitat states (Strain et al., 2014; Benedetti-Cecchi et al., 2015; Ling et al., 2015; Rindi et al., 2017). These degraded states are generally more tolerant of environmental stress, but support lower biodiversity, offer reduced ecosystem functioning, and compromise the delivery of ecosystem services (Filbee-Dexter and Wernberg, 2018).

As the intensity, frequency, duration, and spatial extent of MHWs increase with global warming, their effects on macroalgal forests are expected to exacerbate in the near future (Strain et al., 2014; Oliver et al., 2018; Benedetti-Cecchi, 2021). Accordingly, projections highlight significant contractions in the spatial extent of canopy-forming macroalgae under high-emission climate scenarios by the end of the century (Manca et al., 2024). These findings underscore the urgency of mitigating climate impacts and managing local stressors to preserve the resilience and function of macroalgal ecosystems worldwide.

The Tuscan Archipelago (TA) living lab in BioEcoOcean, is investigating the dynamic relationships between macroalgal forests and extreme warming events. The Mediterranean is a rapidly warming region, and canopy decline is expected to be particularly intense in the basin. Research uses high-resolution temperature measurements to characterise the thermal environment at spatial and temporal scales relevant to benthic organisms (10s of centimetres to 100s of kilometres and from minutes to years). These data will inform not only about the impact of MHWs on macroalgal forests, but also on the role of the algal canopy in moderating extreme thermal events. Preliminary results show that 18% of extreme thermal events that classify as MHWs in the water column are not classified as such underneath algal canopies.

2.2.3 MHW induced compositional shift in Iberian Kelp Forests

Marine ecosystems are currently undergoing profound transformations as communities shift in response to ocean warming and the increasing frequency of MHWs (Smale, 2020; Sousa et al., 2020; Cheng et al., 2022; Smith et al., 2024). These rapid changes are particularly evident in temperate climatic transitional zones, where regions experience tropicalization - a process that involves the incursion of species typically associated with warmer waters (Cheung et al., 2012; Vergés et al., 2014; Pecl et al., 2017; Pessarrodona et al., 2019; Smale, 2020). In these regions, macroalgal communities, including kelp forests, are especially vulnerable, and as a result, many ecological functions can be compromised (Piñeiro-Corbeira et al., 2018).

Such changes are occurring in several regions in the Northeast Atlantic, where the Atlantic living lab in BioEcoOcean also focuses its research. Along the Iberian Peninsula, which naturally features a latitudinal gradient characterised by diverse climatic conditions, high-canopy cold-affinity kelp species, namely *Saccharina latissima* and *Laminaria hyperborea*, are increasingly being replaced by warm-affinity counterparts like *Laminaria ochroleuca* and *Saccorhiza polyschides*. Simultaneously, in the centre-south of the peninsula, these warm-affinity kelps are being replaced by low-canopy, turf-forming species (Azevedo et al., 2023).

This shift toward simplified, low-canopy-dominated assemblages instead of complex, high-canopy kelp forests has multiple ecological repercussions. The tropicalised habitats tend to be structurally poorer, less

productive, and less biodiverse than their predecessors (Ellison et al., 2005; Pessarrodona et al., 2019; Stuart, King and Smale, 2025). Moreover, the change in community structure directly affects critical ecological functions such as productivity, carbon uptake, habitat complexity, and the maintenance of other ecosystem services. Therefore, a decline in the resilience of coastal ecosystems can occur, which in turn has negative implications for economic activities that depend on these systems, notably local fisheries (Smale et al., 2013).

Given the challenges, there is an urgent need for proactive policy responses (Bonebrake et al., 2018; Wilson et al., 2020; Eger et al., 2022; Smith et al., 2024). The identification and protection of climate refugia - areas that offer a buffer against the effects of climate change by providing a more stable climate and maintaining biodiversity (Keppel et al., 2012)- must be prioritized to safeguard vulnerable habitats. In parallel, active restoration efforts involving the re-establishment of kelp populations can and are starting to be implemented. Additionally, integrating MHW metrics into conservation planning is critical, as it provides a more robust framework for predicting and mitigating the impacts of future warming events.

Long-term monitoring programs using different technologies and techniques are equally essential. These programs should emphasise the development of early-warning systems capable of detecting shifts in forest composition and ecosystem function before they reach a critical threshold. By combining continuous monitoring with comprehensive ecological data collection, changes can be anticipated timely, thereby increasing the effectiveness of adaptive management strategies.

2.2.4 The Blob and the Rise of Pyrosomes: Disrupting the Northeast Pacific Food Web

The Blob, an unusually warm water period in the Northeast Pacific in 2013 and the following years, led to substantial changes in the structure and function of regional marine ecosystems (Miller et al., 2019). This event disrupted established ecological connections and had far-reaching consequences for various trophic levels. One of the most notable ecological changes was the dramatic increase in biomass and spread of pyrosomes (*Pyrosoma atlanticum*). These pelagic gelatinous animals (considered tropical to subtropical species) were rarely found in the northeastern Pacific, i.e., north of California, before this event. Pyrosomes were increasingly observed from 2014 until the summer of 2019 when they took unprecedented roles along the entire west coast of North America (Sutherland et al., 2018). The sudden and massive increase in the pyrosome population substantially impacted energy and nutrient flows in the food web. Ecosystem models that compare periods before and after the start of The Blob indicate that *P. atlanticum* consumed a considerable amount of energy previously available to other low-trophic groups, including amphipods, krill, and pteropods (Gomes et al., 2024). The pyrosome blooms likely contributed to a reduction in the biomass of these groups. Most of pyrosome biomass (> 90%) ended up as detritus, which implies that their enormous biomass was only available for higher trophic levels as a food source to a limited extent. Although there are reports that some predators and scavengers are eating pyrosomes (Henschke et al., 2013; Brodeur et al., 2021), they are of lower energetic value compared to traditional prey. Modelling of pelagic food webs that reflect conditions before and after The Blob further showcased cascading (indirect) effects

on various trophic levels. Ecosystem changes (even if temporary) because of MHWs show the potentially complex impacts of extreme warming events on oceanographic conditions and food web functioning. To learn more, please see Luskow 2025.

2.2.5 MHWs and their role in the Arctic ecosystems

MHWs in the Arctic have increased in number over the past decades (Huang et al., 2021). Factors triggering MHWs differ depending on the sea ice cover type, and include abrupt sea ice retreat, precipitation, freshwater dilution processes and elevated air temperature (Barkhordarian et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024). MHWs are predicted to have particularly severe impact on the cold-adopted and sensitive Arctic species while benefiting boreal ones (Frölicher et al., 2018; Pecuchet et al., 2025).

MHWs have been shown to cause shifts in phytoplankton species abundance and composition (e.g., in the North Atlantic (Mills et al., 2013)) and have the potential to increase and intensify primary production in comparably nutrient-rich Arctic waters (Wolf et al., 2024). Since metabolic rates and respiration are temperature-sensitive, elevated temperatures may increase heterotrophic processes and net community respiration altering productivity patterns (Gou et al., 2025; Latorre et al., 2023). Elevated temperatures may surpass physiological boundaries of organisms as well as impact reproduction success and growth rates. For example, in the northern Bering and Chukchi seas during 2017–2019 MHW, lower densities of zooplankton and benthic communities were observed along with an increase in small, low-lipid copepods and a decrease in large, high-lipid copepods (Duffy-Anderson et al., 2019). Accompanied by toxic algal blooms (Huntington et al., 2020; Walsh et al., 2018) these shifts further propagated into the food web and upper trophic levels, including fish and sea birds (Huntington et al., 2020; Pecuchet et al., 2025).

2.2.6 Effects of MHWs on Arctic Zooplankton

The potential effects of MHWs on Arctic marine zooplankton include changes in species composition with increasing abundance of boreal and non-indigenous species, changes in biomass and productivity, and changes in phenology. These types of effects were, to some degree, observed in Gulf of Alaska as a response to a prolonged North Pacific MHW in 2014-2016 (Suryan et al., 2021; Batten et al., 2022; McKinstry et al., 2022). In general, the MHW tended to result in an increase of warm-water associated species, whereas there were no consistent trends for cold-water associated species (Suryan et al., 2021; Batten et al., 2022), including the important large lipid-rich copepods (McKinstry et al., 2022). However, there were indications for changes in diversity of zooplankton, with a lower taxonomic richness after the MHW than before it, and a successful overwintering of a warm-water predatory copepod *Corycaeus anglicus* (Batten et al., 2022), which could change the functioning of the zooplankton community. Also, the phenology of warm-water associated meroplankton and copepods appeared to have shifted, with earlier appearance and longer persistence in the area (Batten et al., 2022). The changes observed in the Arctic were therefore relatively similar to temperate areas, with observations of promoted warm-water species with high temperature tolerance (Gubanova et al., 2022; Winans et al., 2023). In conclusion, the studies on the effects of Arctic

MHWs on zooplankton are scarce, pointing towards modest effects mainly consisting of increased biomass and occurrence of sub-Arctic and boreal species, but little effect on the cold-water species. However, further research is urgently needed.

2.2.7 Understanding Zooplankton and MHWs in the Mediterranean

The zooplankton is a pivotal group in the oceanic ecosystem to understand and model key processes in fish population dynamics, e.g., early life history and recruitment mechanisms in the population (e.g., Menu et al., 2023), as well as the distribution of species, from small pelagic species (sardine, anchovy, mackerel) to baleen whales (Romagosa et al., 2021). The modelling of zooplankton is still limited by the availability of detailed data and the complexity of biogeochemical models. In the meantime, the uncertainty on the impact of climate change on zooplankton is high. It is linked to changes in primary production and a diversity of responses from phytoplankton species, under the effects of changes in temperature, thermal stratification and mixing driven by wind and convection. Gelatinous zooplankton could also benefit from ocean warming and shifts in phytoplankton abundance and diversity towards smaller-sized species. Large pelagic tunicates (gelatinous zooplankton species), for example, are likely to be favoured due to their filter-feeding mode, which gives them access to small preys.

A recent study by Li et al., (2024) took advantage of satellite data and autonomous observations from BioGeoChemical-Argo floats to show that a MHW occurring in the Mediterranean Sea during the 2020 winter drastically inhibited phytoplankton carbon biomass in spring by up to 70%. This was attributed to enhanced stratification limiting the renewal of nutrients from deeper layers, causing an earlier shift of phytoplankton phenology. While zooplankton was not observed with the other variables, simulation outputs from the model SEAPODYM (cf. Pelagic lab 1) showed a coherent similar time shift in the peak of zooplankton biomass, occurring ~1.5 month earlier than on average (Figure 4). The area impacted by the 2020 MHW was located east of the Balearic waters. The western and southern Balearic waters are well known to be a favourable seasonal spawning ground of the Atlantic and Mediterranean bluefin tuna from May to June (Alemany et al. 2010), coinciding with warm waters (> 24 °C) and just following the peak of zooplankton biomass (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Top: Phytoplankton biomass measured by a BGC-ARGO float within the mixed layer in the western Mediterranean Sea (blue continuous line), and regional non-MHW average (blue envelope and dotted line) along the track of the ARGO float. Bottom: Model-derived zooplankton biomass within epipelagic layer ($iZooc$) and non-MHW average. Redrawn from Li et al., (2024).

It can be assumed that a winter MHW affecting the south and west of the Balearic Islands could result in a mismatch between the bluefin tuna spawning season and the presence of prey for larvae and juvenile tuna. There are regular sampling studies of bluefin tuna larvae around the Balearic Islands, and one study (Reglero et al., 2025) indicates that 2020 was effectively a year of low larvae density compared to 2022, i.e.: 0.27 (± 0.52) m⁻³ vs 1.16 (± 3.7) m⁻³, respectively. However, the trends were opposite for zooplankton sampled at the same stations, highlighting the difficulty of establishing a direct correlation between environmental factors and bluefin tuna recruitment success despite a regular sampling effort.

2.3 Identification of critical EOVS Sub-variables

To better understand the effects of MHWs on marine life, we need to understand what to measure, when to measure and how to do it. For example, in-situ physical, biogeochemical and biology & ecosystem observations (e.g., temperature, phytoplankton and zooplankton abundances and species diversity) located in areas and time periods where MHWs occurred need to be identified to conduct impact studies. MHW indicators based on SST satellite data exhibit a strong potential for detecting offshore MHWs due to the high spatio-temporal resolution and coverage of these datasets. In addition, to get a measure of how the MHW extends vertically, the mixed-layer depth, thermocline depth or heat content integrated over a certain depth constitute critical [data products](#) which are derived from physical observations, in particular the Sea Surface Temperature and the Subsurface Temperature EOVS. Other physical EOVS which are important for understanding drivers and predictors of MHW occurrence and displacement include: Surface Currents EOVS, Subsurface Currents EOVS (needed to provide information on heat advection), Ocean Surface

Heat Flux EOV (since MHWs are typically driven by heat gain from the atmosphere or lack of latent heat loss to the atmosphere), and Sea State EOV (low winds being strongly linked to MHW occurrence).

Similar approaches can be used to identify MHW indicators of associated extreme events in biological and biogeochemical phenomena. These could include the use of:

- data on primary production and/or chlorophyll a concentration to inform on primary production decrease/increase;
- data on dissolved oxygen concentration to inform on deoxygenation; or
- data on pH or aragonite saturation ($\Omega_{\text{aragonite}}$) to inform on ocean acidification

For instance, when $\Omega_{\text{aragonite}}$ falls below 1, the ocean becomes undersaturated with respect to aragonite, making it difficult for some marine organisms to build and maintain their shells and skeletons. This can have significant ecological impacts, particularly on species like corals, molluscs, and some plankton. To explore the change in species/size community structures due to the impact of MHWs, one needs to consider At the biological level, sub-variables that identify measuring changes in functional type distribution of phytoplankton, zooplankton and micronekton - sub-variables or derived products of the Phytoplankton Biomass and Diversity EOV, and the Zooplankton Biomass and Diversity EOV. Harmonization, not to mention standardisation, of the sampling methods related to these measurements remains an issue and requires a large effort at the global research community level. Currently, we lack adequate datasets and data products which would enable consistent model evaluation of the impact of MHWs on these structural and functional ecosystem properties at regional and global levels. A first step would be to consider each existing sampling program separately before combining them together in a single dataset that can be used to calibrate and validate models. However, there are established ecosystem sampling programs worldwide which have the potential to investigate the impact of MHW and associated extreme events by providing time series datasets as a basis for adequate indicator development and testing. These include but are not limited to the regions of the eastern Pacific (CALCOFI), the North-East Pacific (Line P), the North Pacific (ECOFOCI), the subtropical north Pacific (HOT) and Atlantic (BATS) regions, as well as the Barents Sea (IMR).

2.4 Current state of links between MHWs and OBIS

The Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS) has not yet produced outputs specifically addressing MHWs or their impacts on marine biodiversity. This gap highlights an opportunity to better integrate biodiversity data with MHWs monitoring to improve understanding and response strategies. However, GOOS has established a MHWs Exemplar under the [Co-Design program](#). This initiative aims to identify pilot areas for studying MHWs and lay the groundwork for broader monitoring efforts. Members of this Exemplar are already involved in both BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim.

OBIS is currently exploring a project proposal to investigate MHWs that would leverage tools already under development that focus on species' physiological limits and thermal traits, using its own data and from

other databases like WoRMS (World Register of Marine Species). These tools can be used to predict how species and ecosystems respond to MHW events. The proposal is looking to include innovative approaches to strengthen and improve models to implement early warning systems that would help communities prepare for MHWs. Innovative approaches could include, for example, using eDNA to conduct pre- and post- MHW assessments to provide insights on species-specific impacts and community shifts. These models could be refined using real-world data from observed MHW events, fostering a feedback loop to enhance accuracy.

3. Clustering Event I - Deep Dive into the Blue Frontier

3.1 Objectives and Structure of Clustering Event I

Recognising the need for collective action, the BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim projects organised a clustering event (March 2025) aimed at advancing ocean observation methodologies and strategies. More than 30 relevant European and international initiatives and projects were represented, such as [SEA-Quester](#), [BioBoost+](#), [IMDOS](#), [Ocean Best Practice](#), and the [European Polar Board](#). The event focused on identifying challenges in integrating physics, biogeochemistry, and biology & ecosystems EOVs, exploring solutions for EOVI indicators (combination of variables), enhancing interdisciplinary collaboration in ocean observation and policy development, and developing policy recommendations to strengthen global ocean observing and monitoring efforts.

The primary objectives of the clustering event were:

1. **To strengthen the implementation and integration of EOVI-based global observing systems.** EOVI, managed by GOOS, are critical for assessing ocean health and its interactions with Earth systems. The objective is to advance interdisciplinary collaboration to refine methodologies for monitoring and forecasting ocean changes, thereby supporting future contributions to global climate and biodiversity assessments and early warning systems.
2. **To promote integration across physical, biogeochemical, and biological & ecosystem domains.** The aim is to foster a holistic approach to ocean data collection that captures the interconnectedness of oceanic processes. This integration is intended to improve understanding of the ocean's role in climate regulation and ecosystem dynamics, while addressing existing gaps in coordinated biological and ecosystem observations.
3. **To advance the development of a standardised ocean observing framework that informs policy and economic decision-making.** The objective is to ensure that ocean data is accessible, comparable, and interoperable to support evidence-based policymaking and sustainable economic practices related to ocean resources. This includes generating actionable recommendations to guide future policy applications and strengthen links between observation systems and decision-making processes.

To achieve these objectives, the event was organised into the following four focused sessions:

EOV Speed Dating: This interactive session facilitated exchanges among participants to discuss advancements, challenges, and collaborative opportunities related to specific EOVs. The format encouraged cross-disciplinary discussion, understanding, and the formulation of EOV partnerships aimed at refining observation methodologies and data utilization.

Bridging the Land-Coast-Ocean Nexus: Addressing the continuum of terrestrial environments to the open ocean, this session explored methodologies for integrating observations across these domains, emphasising the importance of cohesive monitoring strategies that encompass land-sea interactions, which are vital for understanding, for example, nutrient fluxes, pollutant pathways, and sediment transport.

MHWs: Given the increasing frequency and impact of MHWs on marine ecosystems and coastal communities, the session focused on identifying observation requirements, and understanding the implications of these extreme events on marine ecosystems.

Identifying Issues and Barriers in Ocean Observing: This session aimed to pinpoint existing challenges in ocean observation systems, including technological limitations, data accessibility, and coordination gaps and to propose actionable solutions to overcome these barriers.

By uniting expertise from both projects, the clustering event served as a catalyst for advancing ocean observing practices toward a more comprehensive, cost-effective, and coordinated approach to ocean monitoring and sustainable management. The recommendations developed during these sessions are instrumental in informing policymakers, guiding sustainable ocean management and enhancing the coherence of the global ocean observation and assessment community.

3.2 Introducing the sister projects

[BioEcoOcean](#) - Co-Creating Transformative Pathways to Biological and Ecosystem Ocean Observations - and [ObsSea4Clim](#) - Ocean observations and indicators for climate and assessments - aim to advance ocean observation methodologies and enhance our understanding and management of ocean systems to support climate and biodiversity assessments.

The ultimate goal of BioEcoOcean is to enhance the biology & ecosystem ocean observing capacity for advancing scientific understanding of the ocean and increasing the utility of ocean observations. One important component is to transform biological and ecosystem ocean observations through the development of the Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science. This comprehensive tool is designed to guide ocean observing programs at all stages, from planning to policy application, promoting a holistic and collaborative approach across the ocean observing value chain. The project engages stakeholders in co-creating the Blueprint to enhance communication and cooperation among various sectors involved in ocean observation. BioEcoOcean also focuses on accelerating the implementation of biology & ecosystems EOVs to improve global biodiversity and ecosystem assessments while strengthening common approaches and standards through the development of standardised methodologies for observations. Furthermore, a

key focus of BioEcoOcean is improving the understanding of the links between ocean biodiversity, biogeochemistry, and climate using interdisciplinary approaches and advanced technologies. BioEcoOcean prioritises capacity building and collaboration with global ocean observation initiatives to promote widespread adoption of its co-produced standards.

ObsSea4Clim aims to enhance the framework for European nations' contributions to ocean observations, with a strong focus on physical EOVs and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) and their use for the implementation of the Rolling review of requirements (RRR), as defined in the Manual on the World Meteorological Organization (WMO) Integrated Global Observing System. The RRR process compiles information about requirements for observations, about observing system capabilities, their cost-effectiveness, and draws on experts and impact studies to provide guidance on the most important priorities for addressing the gaps between requirements and capabilities. These efforts support both regional and global climate assessments, refine projections, and develop actionable indicators for sustainable development. The project seeks to create new ocean indicators that inform sustainable practices, advance Earth System Models (ESMs) by integrating EOVs and ECVs to reduce uncertainties in climate projections and establish an interoperable data ecosystem that serves multidisciplinary needs across oceanic and climatic studies. Additionally, ObsSea4Clim prioritises the development of standardized methods for both in situ and satellite observations to ensure data consistency and reliability.

Both ObsSea4Clim and BioEcoOcean highlight the significance of collaborative efforts and standardised practices in ocean observation. By working across disciplines and engaging with a broad range of stakeholders, projects contribute to strengthening climate resilience and fostering sustainable ocean management.

3.3 Essential Ocean Variables: Physics and Biology & Ecosystems (the EOVS speed dating)

The EOVS Speed Dating workshop session marked one of the first instances where experts from the fields of biology & ecosystems, and physics were brought together in a collaborative setting. This was a significant milestone in fostering interdisciplinary dialogue and cooperation. It was an achievement in its own right that lays the groundwork for future innovations in ocean observation and climate solutions.

The EOVS Speed Dating workshop was designed with multiple objectives in mind (please see Nordlund et al., 2025 for more information). First, it served as an icebreaker, allowing participants to build understanding across different scientific fields. Participants from the BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim projects, which respectively focus on biology & ecosystem EOVS and physics and climate EOVS, were introduced to one another and encouraged to collaborate. The workshop sought to enhance understanding of EOVS by facilitating discussions on their characteristics, sub-variables, and relevance to ocean observing. Through these interactions, the participants were expected to identify potential synergies that could contribute to more comprehensive ocean observing, ultimately addressing challenges related to climate and ecosystem changes.

The workshop was structured into three rounds followed by an open-floor discussion. In the first round, participants were grouped with colleagues from different fields to familiarise themselves with EOVs across disciplines. The discussions in this phase revolved around understanding the attributes, sub-variables, and importance of these variables to different fields. In the second round, participants were tasked with exploring potential collaborations by discussing how biology & ecosystem EOVs could pair with physical EOVs. This phase focused on identifying synergies and collaborations that could improve ocean observing. The third round encouraged participants to translate these relationships into practical collaborations, discussing potential joint research opportunities, product development ideas, and other innovative concepts. Finally, the open-floor discussion allowed groups to share their key findings and propose further steps for collaboration.

The workshop resulted in several key discussion points. Participants explored the interconnectedness of EOVs across biology & ecosystem and physics (Table 1), noting variables such as subsurface temperature and ocean colour. Notably, subsurface temperature was identified as a crucial parameter, as it influences various biological variables, including phytoplankton biomass, species composition, fish abundance, and benthic invertebrates (Figure 5). The importance of considering how living habitats can affect physical parameters (like temperature or currents) was also highlighted. Other discussions highlighted the relationship between ocean colour and biological sub-variables like phytoplankton biomass and macroalgae coverage. For example, changes in ocean colour could indicate shifts in phytoplankton composition, affecting the downward flux of organic matter and the benthic ecosystems that rely on it.

Figure 5: Subsurface temperature, a key physical EOV, affects several biology & ecosystem EOVs. While multiple physical EOVs interact with biological processes, temperature plays a significant role in shaping the distribution, abundance, and diversity of organisms such as fish, zooplankton, phytoplankton, seagrass, and macroalgae. This simplified diagram focuses on subsurface temperature's influence within the scope of this document, acknowledging that other physical EOVs also impact biological and ecosystem dynamics (biology & ecosystems EOVs from top left: Fish abundance and distribution; Phytoplankton biomass and diversity; Zooplankton biomass and diversity; Seagrass cover and composition; Macroalgal canopy cover and composition; Hard Coral cover and composition, and Invertebrate abundance and distribution).

Table 1. Examples of EOV relationships identified during the workshop.

Biology & ecosystem EOVs	Physics EOVs	Example of identified Relationships
Phytoplankton biomass and diversity & Benthic invertebrate abundance and distribution	Subsurface temperature	Subsurface temperature influences growth, with potential effects on species composition and distribution.
Fish abundance and distribution	Subsurface temperature	Subsurface temperature changes affect habitat suitability for fish, influencing their abundance, species composition and distribution. Many biology & ecosystem EOVs are also affected.
Macroalgal canopy cover and composition & Phytoplankton biomass and diversity	Sea ice	Sea ice coverage affects light penetration, which in turn influences macroalgal and phytoplankton growth and distribution.
Phytoplankton biomass and diversity & Benthic invertebrate abundance and distribution	Ocean colour	A change in ocean colour may indicate a change in phytoplankton composition and thus "health" of the open-ocean primary producer population (also influenced by sub surface temperature). This is then connected to a potentially increasing rate of downward flux of dying/dead phytoplankton feeding the benthic invertebrates (filter feeders). Hence, a change in water colour could be linked to the biomass, present/absence, percent coverage of benthic invertebrates.

Several challenges and knowledge gaps were also identified during the session. Participants found it difficult to understand and integrate technical terms and acronyms across the different EOV sub-variables from distinct fields. Additionally, there were gaps in understanding how certain physics EOVs, such as ocean pressure, impact biological variables. A key challenge was the development of EOVs in silos (Figure 1), which complicates interdisciplinary collaboration. A recognition of the need for more explicit connections between EOVs was identified. There were also issues related to the measurement of certain variables, such as biomass and percent cover, and how these variables relate to physical parameters like currents and temperature. Scale mismatches between physical and biological variables were another challenge, as different scales (cm to 1000s of kilometres) can lead to inconsistencies when integrating data.

Potential solutions emerged from these discussions. Participants proposed involving a broader range of EOV experts to provide comprehensive feedback on the EOV specification sheets, and in the future, consider sub-variables to cover all relevant biological/ecosystems, physical, and biogeochemical functions. Fostering interdisciplinary research to explore how physical variables, such as ocean pressure, impact biological EOVs through additional studies and model development was also suggested. Integrated models that include both biology & ecosystem and physics variables could be developed to create cross-field data products and reduce uncertainties. For example, linking phytoplankton biomass to changes in sea surface temperature, currents, and sea ice cover could enhance understanding of how physical changes influence biological processes. The use of AI tools and integrated data products, combining satellite and in-situ sensor data, were proposed as potential methods to address the issue of scale mismatches.

Looking ahead, several next steps were identified. The participants agreed to continue building connections between biology & ecosystem and physics EOVs, particularly by focusing on the relationships between phytoplankton biomass and ocean colour, with the aim to develop data products that integrate these

variables and enhance ocean observation systems. Participants also discussed the need to explore whether existing data products or models could be used to understand how changes in subsurface temperature, sea ice coverage, and ocean colour influence biology & ecosystem EOVs, or if new models would need to be developed. To bridge the gap between different scales scaling down satellite data with in-situ sensors was another area for future focus to improve integration of physics and biology & ecosystem variables. Finally, follow-up workshops were proposed to further explore strategies for integrating biology & ecosystem and physics EOVs.

In conclusion, the EOV speed dating session underscored the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in enhancing ocean observations and developing solutions for climate and ecosystem challenges. Participants emphasized the need for closer integration between biology & ecosystems, and physics EOVs to develop more comprehensive monitoring frameworks. The session underscored the value of standardised monitoring protocols and comparable ocean data in enhancing scientific research and policy applications. The workshop highlighted the value of shared knowledge and cross-field learning, and participants identified several opportunities for future collaborations and innovations in ocean observing. The insights gained from this session will contribute to broader European Commission initiatives such as DTO, Copernicus Marine Service, the EU4Ocean Coalition, aimed at improving ocean observation and climate research, while also providing essential guidance for policymakers in shaping future marine conservation and climate resilience strategies.

3.4 Bridging Land, Coastal, and Ocean Observing Systems – Integrating Physical, Biogeochemical, and Biological Data for Comprehensive Data Products

This session explored the need for integrated ocean observation systems that bridge land, coastal, and open-ocean environments, highlighting how processes across physical, biogeochemical, and biological domains are deeply interconnected. Presentations covered diverse topics, from the impacts of glacier retreat and changing sea surface temperatures, to the decline of mussel populations in response to environmental change. A key theme was the value of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) in capturing these cross-cutting dynamics. The session emphasized that understanding and responding to changes in ocean health requires collaborative approaches, multi-source data integration, and stronger connections between science and policy.

One of the presentations showed that a rise in SST can lead to glacier melt, increasing suspended matter in the water, and trigger regime shifts. The retreat of glaciers alters surface ocean properties such as light availability and nutrient levels, which affect marine ecosystems. The discussion also highlighted the role of EOVs and ECVs, across multiple domains, including atmospheric (temperature, precipitation, wind speed), terrestrial (glacial and river discharge, geology), and oceanic (biological and physical processes, particulate matter) variables. A key emphasis was placed on the interconnected nature of EOVs, advocating for a shift from isolated observation to a globally integrated system. These variables are critical for understanding ocean health and operate across varying spatial and temporal scales. The GOOS EOVs provide valuable in-

situ data that serves multiple purposes, including operational services, climate monitoring and ocean health assessments. Additionally, a presentation and following discussions linked temperature fluctuations to the decline in Irish mussel populations, underscoring the need for adaptive data use and innovation. Moreover, the session stressed the need for regional validation of satellite products, particularly at small spatial scales.

Several key challenges and knowledge gaps were identified, primarily concerning the limitations of data resolution, integration, and consistency. One major issue is the temporal and spatial discrepancies among different data types, which complicate comprehensive data analysis. Furthermore, high-resolution satellite data is essential for many studies, but cloud cover often hinders observations, particularly when investigating plumes. The integration of diverse data points from various sources remains a complex task, requiring standardised methodologies for consistency and usability. Coastal data represents another significant challenge due to its discontinuity and dynamic nature, making it difficult to obtain reliable datasets. The inconsistencies in temporal scales further necessitate rigorous quality control to improve data reliability. A crucial concern is the challenge of translating EOVs into actionable insights for policymakers, transferring scientific findings effectively to inform decision-making processes.

To address these challenges, several innovative solutions were proposed. Machine learning techniques, coupled with drop cameras, could be employed to enhance biological data collection within the water column, improving our understanding of marine ecosystems. Integrating biological sensors onto existing platforms that already collect physical EOVs, such as gliders and Argo floats, can economically and efficiently fill the knowledge gaps in biology & ecosystem EOVs. Moreover, the use of drones to photograph e.g. plumes offers a viable alternative to mitigate the issue of cloud cover obstructing satellite observations. Interdisciplinary approaches and open data formats were emphasized as key strategies to improve data accessibility and usability. Standardising units and scales across disciplines would facilitate better integration of datasets, while leveraging AI tools for data analysis could enhance the extraction of meaningful insights, provided that datasets are reliable and consistent. Collaboration with local communities and industries in data collection efforts could also expand the scope of in-situ observations, offering valuable supplementary data for scientific research. Effective communication regarding the importance and applicability of EOVI indicators for policymakers was highlighted as an essential step in bridging the gap between research and policy. Encouraging discussions on how these indicators can be tailored to meet stakeholders' needs would further help ensure that collected data serves practical and strategic purposes.

Moving forward, collaboration across various disciplines and engagement with stakeholders will be crucial in advancing ocean observation efforts. Strengthening cross-disciplinary collaboration and actively involving stakeholders in decision-making processes will help create a more integrated and effective observational framework. Defining key research questions and assessing whether existing knowledge and indicators are sufficient to address them will also be essential in refining data collection strategies. As in one example, expanding the range of EOVs to include biogeochemical and biological factors would significantly enhance research on mussel populations and other ecological aspects, broadening the scope of ocean health assessments. Furthermore, the validation of regional satellite products at finer spatial

scales is necessary to improve their applicability and reliability in local contexts. By addressing these challenges through technological advancements, interdisciplinary collaboration, and improved data standardisation, the session highlighted the importance of a holistic approach to ocean observation. These steps will enhance our understanding of ocean health and inform better policy and conservation strategies moving forward.

3.5 MHWs in space and time: understanding thermal anomalies at ecologically relevant scale

MHWs are periods of unusually high sea surface temperatures that persist for days to months and extend over large oceanic regions. They result from a combination of atmospheric and oceanographic processes, including changes in ocean currents, reduced water mixing and persistent high-pressure systems, which can influence regional climates, generating droughts, floods and cyclones. As climate change progresses, MHWs are becoming more frequent, intense and prolonged, posing growing threats to marine biodiversity, ecosystem services as well as affecting human safety and food security.

MHWs are typically defined relative to historical temperature baselines, that is the climatological mean over a multi-year period used to compute the thermal anomaly. However, defining MHWs remains challenging. A widely accepted definition is that of Hobday et al., (2016), where MHWs occur when sea temperatures exceed the 90th percentile of the long-term local climatology for at least five consecutive days. While considering this definition a reliable standard approach, the session discussed potential limitations and areas of improvement, including the lack of objective criteria to identify critical thresholds to define temperature anomalies and baselines. In particular, the session discussed the need for a definition that considers the impact of MHWs on organisms (Amaya et al., 2023). This requires a better understanding of the thermal safety margins of marine species such that the definitions of thermal anomalies and baselines have a biological meaning. A consensus seems to emerge for adopting a shifting-baseline approach, particularly for MHW indicators using SST data. This approach is preferred to keep track of the dynamics of MHWs in the context of overall ocean warming. The session emphasized the importance of spatial resolution, distinguishing between coastal and open-ocean contexts, and the use of both satellite-derived and in-situ data to detect MHWs. Innovative detection programs, including AI-based forecasting tools from Mercator Ocean International, are under development and may offer high-resolution, localised MHW forecasts. For more information, please see Lehodey (2025).

The impacts of MHWs are far-reaching, especially in coastal ecosystems. They can lead to mass mortalities, coral bleaching, harmful algal blooms, the spread of non-indigenous species, and disruptions in food webs, see e.g. the case studies in Chapter 2 in this document. Additionally, MHWs can disrupt the seasonal cycle of phytoplankton spring bloom and subsequent production of zooplankton, potentially leading to a mismatch between zooplankton peaks and reproductive phenology of many fish species. Such mismatch can increase larval mortality and limit recruitment in older age classes, with cascading effects in the whole food web up to the higher predators, disrupting marine biodiversity. The biological responses to MHWs on

marine organisms in these cases are an increase in the basal metabolic rates, leading to an energy demand that can exceed the metabolic capacity of the species. Consequences are either an increase in mortality rate, lower growth, or reproductive outputs to compensate the increase in metabolism. Other consequences include the movement of mobile species and/or the replacement by other more adapted ones.

In offshore environments, MHWs contribute to species redistribution and pelagic fish stock loss. These thermal anomalies are also most often associated with decreased primary production, although some counter-directional exceptions have been noted, especially in cold water (e.g., Arctic) systems (Bouchard et al., 2017; LeBlanc et al., 2020). Other extreme events can occur together with MHWs, such as deoxygenation and ocean acidification. It is also critical to consider the vertical extension of the MHWs in the ocean, from the bottom to the surface, from open ocean to shallow waters. Therefore, in addition to satellite data, in-situ monitoring remains an essential source of knowledge. Mooring networks and autonomous sensors like Argo floats are key observing systems for monitoring the impact of MHWs on multiple essential physical and biogeochemical variables throughout the vertical water column.

Robust indicators need to be defined to enable real-time monitoring and forecasting of MHWs and other related extreme events, and to support effective communication with stakeholders. A multi- and interdisciplinary approach was proposed to integrate existing indicators and models to predict MHWs impacts on marine species and ecosystems. Future steps include combining reprocessed satellite SST data with FerryBox and Argo float data and creating tailored data products, such as maps and spatially-resolved forecasts, to aid decision-making. Coordination among project partners is essential to these efforts.

3.6 Identification of key issues and barriers in ocean observing

Ocean observing and monitoring oceanic changes through EOVs is necessary to address pressing environmental challenges such as the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) variability, land-coast-ocean interactions, MHWs, and the development of ocean observation models and projections. This session explored the motivations, challenges, solutions, and policy actions necessary for improving ocean monitoring systems. In-depth group discussions with participants spanning both physics and biology & ecosystem expertise were held.

3.6.1. Key Challenges in Ocean Observations

Several key challenges were identified during this session. To provide a comprehensive understanding of ocean dynamics EOVs must be observed across multiple spatial and temporal scales. However, integrating physical, biogeochemical, and biology & ecosystem data remains challenging due to mismatches in resolution and observation frequency. Large-scale systems like the AMOC require synchronisation between datasets from different disciplines to ensure meaningful analyses. Additionally, monitoring the land-coast-ocean continuum is essential for addressing coastal erosion, pollution, and habitat degradation. The fragmentation of ocean monitoring initiatives at national, regional, and international levels further hinders

effective data sharing and integration.

Ocean models depend on in-situ data for validation, yet data collection efforts remain insufficient. While substantial datasets exist, they are often underutilised, and the translation of raw data into actionable information remains limited. Real-time and historical datasets should be integrated into ocean models to enhance the accuracy of projections. Standardising data formats, improving real-time observation capabilities, and fostering cross-border collaboration are critical for enhancing model accuracy and utility. Expanding coastal observation initiatives and improving MHW forecasting by defining thresholds and indicators at different spatial and temporal scales can strengthen ocean monitoring frameworks. Additionally, biogeochemical responses should be incorporated into MHW definitions to enhance adaptive management strategies. Transparency in uncertainty reporting can also boost the credibility of ocean observing data.

The limited interdisciplinary collaboration between scientists, policymakers, and industry stakeholders prevents a holistic approach to ocean observing and monitoring. Poor integration between land, coastal, and open ocean observations results in knowledge gaps that impact decision-making.

3.6.2. Potential Solutions for Improved Ocean Observations

Three potential solutions for improved ocean observations were especially highlighted during the session and those were:

Enhancing Data Scale and Integration: Improving spatial and temporal resolution through multiple observation platforms, such as autonomous vehicles and satellites, can enhance data integration. Equipping Argo floats with additional sensors, including cameras, can facilitate the collection of both physical and biological data. Downscaling approaches are also essential to make large-scale observations relevant at regional and local levels. Targeted observations at AMOC hotspots will improve the accuracy of climate projections and support climate change mitigation strategies.

Expanding Data Availability and Validation: Developing low-cost ocean health sensors and engaging citizen scientists, such as fishers, can expand in-situ data collection. Adhering to FAIR data principles will improve data accessibility and usability. Additionally, integrating terrestrial, coastal, and oceanic datasets can bridge existing knowledge gaps in land-coast-ocean interactions. Strengthening observational efforts for MHWs and incorporating biological indicators into monitoring frameworks will enhance predictive capabilities and support marine ecosystem resilience.

Strengthening Coordination and Collaboration: Encouraging interdisciplinary collaboration between scientists, policymakers, and industry stakeholders can align data needs with research efforts. Establishing coordination mechanisms across national and international observation networks will prevent redundancy and improve efficiency. Modellers should be included in the co-design of the observation systems from the planning stage, to ensure improved workflows. Standardising data formats and fostering knowledge exchange will further strengthen global coordination efforts. Moreover, leveraging technological

advancements, such as real-time sensors and advanced modelling techniques, can enhance ocean observation systems and their contribution to climate resilience and sustainable ocean management.

Improving ocean monitoring systems requires overcoming data scale mismatches, increasing data availability, and enhancing interdisciplinary collaboration. Understanding of critical ocean tipping points, such as the risks of changes to the AMOC is also vital to inform policy decisions. Policy actions should prioritise standardisation, data accessibility, and the integration of biology & ecosystem variables into existing ocean observing and monitoring frameworks. Strengthening global coordination efforts and leveraging technological advancements can improve more effective ocean observation, ultimately contributing to climate resilience and sustainable ocean management.

4. Co-production of Policy Recommendations

Building on the technical and collaborative pathways identified in enhanced observational platforms, data integration and validation, and cross-sector coordination, this chapter presents policy recommendations that leverage EOVs to strengthen the monitoring and management of marine ecosystems. Emphasising integrated, interdisciplinary approaches aligned with sustainable development objectives and the European Green Deal targets, these recommendations call for standardised data formats, FAIR data accessibility, stakeholder co-design, targeted funding mechanisms, and adaptive regulatory frameworks with advances in ocean observation to directly reinforce the ocean–climate–biodiversity nexus. The following policy recommendations have been developed based on the collaborative discussions between physics and biology & ecosystem experts during the clustering event I and beyond. For each of the policy recommendations, we have also explored the literature to support these recommendations.

4.1 Policy recommendations brought forward from this process

4.1.1 Support and encourage the use of EOVs

We recommend supporting and encouraging the use of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) to establish a standardised framework for observing and understanding the ocean system across physical, biogeochemical, and biology & ecosystem domains. EOVs, identified by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), are critical variables that are globally interoperable and support climate and biodiversity assessments, biodiversity conservation, and early warning systems. However, biology & ecosystem EOVs variables remain underrepresented in current global observation frameworks, limiting our ability to evaluate climate impacts on marine ecosystems (Miloslavich et al 2018; Sloyan et al., 2019; Tanhua et al., 2019a). Policies should prioritise encouraging the use of EOVs and especially the use of biology & ecosystem EOVs and support the development of standardised ocean indicators to enhance informed decision-making for conservation and sustainable ocean management.

4.1.2 Upgrade and Diversify Observation Platforms

We recommend that national and regional policy frameworks prioritise investment in a broader range of advanced ocean observation platforms to improve data quality and coverage across physical, biogeochemical, and biology & ecosystem domains. Investing in various advanced ocean observation tools such as autonomous vehicles, multi-sensor Argo floats, and high-resolution satellites has been shown to greatly improve the collection of detailed physical, biogeochemical, and biological data (Chai et al., 2020; Saad et al., 2020). This investment should be supported by funding programmes at the national and regional levels to encourage innovation and ensure the interoperability among different observation systems.

4.1.3 Addressing Scale Mismatch

We recommend that policy frameworks actively support and address scale mismatch by promoting the integration of observations and data systems across spatial and temporal scales. This is particularly important because ecosystem changes are driven by processes operating at multiple, and often mismatched, spatial and temporal scales, from fine-scale species interactions to broad-scale environmental shifts (Trifonova et al., 2022). Furthermore, the temporal scale at which shifts in biological systems can be detected will vary depending on the specific EOVs, the properties being monitored, and the length of the existing time-series (Miloslavich et al., 2018). To address this scale mismatch, policy frameworks should promote collaboration between projects, organisations and agencies managing satellite data and those operating localised sensor networks (Howe et al., 2020) and conducting in situ investigations for a consistent integration of broad satellite observations with detailed in situ measurements across global and local contexts.

4.1.4 Implement Downscaling and Targeted Observation Strategies

We recommend that policy frameworks support the development and integration of downscaling methodologies and targeted observation strategies to improve the relevance and usability of global ocean data at regional and local levels. Development of downscaling methodologies that convert global oceanic data into actionable, regional insights is particularly important in areas such as AMOC hotspots and vulnerable coastal zones. Evidence from region-specific case studies shows that downscaling techniques are effective in improving local forecasts, including predictions of coastal erosion and habitat loss (see e.g. Antolínez et al., 2018). Policy actions should integrate these methods into existing programs and support pilot projects in diverse environmental contexts.

4.1.5 Support for Integrated Ocean Observing Systems

We recommend that policy frameworks prioritise sustained funding and coordination for the development of integrated ocean observing systems that bring together biological, biogeochemical, and physical Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs). Allocate funding toward initiatives that foster interdisciplinary research and combine biological, biogeochemical, and physical EOVs into unified observing systems. Evidence confirms that integrated systems deliver more reliable and comprehensive assessments of ecosystem dynamics and enhance the accuracy of climate predictions (Thurston et al., 2021). Policy development should establish international funding programmes that support and encourage cross-disciplinary projects and build integrated ocean observing networks at national, regional and global levels.

4.1.6 Standardisation of Data Collection Protocols

We recommend that policy frameworks support the harmonisation of data collection protocols across institutions and borders to ensure data interoperability and comparability. Harmonise data collection protocols across national and international organizations. Comparative research demonstrates that standardised methodologies significantly improve data interoperability and facilitate meta-analyses critical for global environmental assessments (Tanhua et al., 2019b). Policies should leverage the coordinating role of international organisations and regional alliances to standardise guidelines for enabling interoperability of data sharing and integration.

4.1.7 Investment in AI and Data Analytics

We recommend that policy frameworks prioritise sustained investment in AI technologies and advanced modelling tools to improve the processing, interpretation, and application of ocean observation data. Promoting and investing in advanced AI tools and modelling techniques enhances the synthesis of ocean observation data and reduces uncertainty in predictive analyses. Studies have shown that AI-driven analytics greatly increases the speed and accuracy of trend detection within complex datasets (Saad et al., 2020), thereby overcoming limitations of traditional methods. Policy frameworks should encourage public-private partnerships that fund research in trustworthy AI applications for ocean science while mandating the integration of these tools across governmental and research institutions acting in compliance with the European AI Strategy and supporting the AI Continent Action Plan.

4.1.8 Adopt FAIR Data Principles and Enhance Dataset Integration

We recommend truly mandating adherence to Open Science, FAIR and Directive 2007/2/EC (INSPIRE) principles for all marine datasets to enhance their utility in research and policy-making. Integrated data platforms, such as the UNESCO-IOC Ocean Biodiversity and Information System (OBIS), provide excellent examples of how FAIR principles can be applied in practice to enhance data accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. Such initiatives accelerate scientific discovery, improve research reproducibility, and

ultimately lead to better-informed policy outcomes. Policies should require adherence to Open Science and FAIR principles in research funding and research project evaluations, along with promoting international data-sharing agreements.

4.1.9 Promote Low-Cost Sensor Development and Citizen Science Initiatives

We recommend promoting the development of low-cost, high-precision sensors and supporting citizen science initiatives to expand spatial and temporal coverage of marine data. This includes fostering the development of low-cost, high-precision sensors and actively engaging local communities, such as fishers and coastal inhabitants, in citizen science projects to expand spatial and temporal data coverage. Evidence from various coastal studies indicates that when standardised low-cost monitoring technologies are combined with citizen science, data networks can be substantially expanded and enriched with localized insights (Marcelli et al., 2021). Policy measures should support programs that provide funding, training, and equipment for local monitoring efforts.

4.1.10 Encourage Cross-Sectoral Collaboration

We recommend developing policy frameworks that incentivise cross-sectoral collaboration to ensure ocean observation data is effectively translated into actionable policy insights. Such frameworks should promote and incentivise cooperation among scientists, data managers, industry and decision-makers. Given that scientific evaluation is inherently connected to political, cultural, and social dynamics, investing in effective communication and fostering engagement across interdisciplinary networks is essential. Interdisciplinary collaboration that align ocean observations with societal needs—such as food security, human health, and ecosystem services—enhance the adoption of best practices in environmental monitoring and support the practical application of research findings (Mackenzie et al., 2019; Satterthwaite et al. 2021). Policies should incorporate research grants and establish interagency working groups to foster regular communication among stakeholders.

4.1.11 Regular interdisciplinary workshops and trainings

We recommend securing funding for regular interdisciplinary workshops and training sessions to facilitate knowledge exchange and build capacity among experts in ocean monitoring and management. Allocate and secure funding for regular interdisciplinary workshops and training sessions that facilitate knowledge exchange among experts in ocean monitoring and management. Interdisciplinary knowledge exchange is essential to develop methods that integrate insights across scales, enabling a more effective understanding, quantification, and prediction of climate impacts on marine ecosystem services (McDonald et al., 2018). Policy frameworks should integrate interdisciplinary capacity-building components into existing educational and vocational training programs and support regular trainings at both the national and international levels.

4.1.12 Incorporate Biogeochemical and Biological Data

We recommend mandating the systematic integration of biogeochemical and biological indicators into ocean observation programs to provide a more comprehensive assessment of ecosystem health and marine biodiversity. Mandate the systematic integration of biogeochemical and biological indicators within ocean observation programs to provide a comprehensive assessment of ecosystem health and marine biodiversity. Research demonstrates that inclusion of biological metrics alongside physical data not only improves early detection of ecological disturbances but also enhances adaptive management responses (Miloslavich et al. 2018; 2024; Muller-Karger et al 2024). Policies should update existing monitoring guidelines to require biological data collection and analysis, and support research to develop new biological indicators.

4.1.13 Integrate biological responses to exceptional warm periods

We recommend allocating funding to investigate the impacts of exceptional warm periods on marine life by systematically analysing existing time-series data. This should include examination of ecological responses regardless of whether the effects are strong or subtle. A literature review highlights a regional bias in studies of MHWs, with significantly fewer investigations conducted in European countries, underscoring the need for broader geographic representation to achieve a more balanced scientific understanding (Joyce et al., 2024). Policy measures should design funding programs that encourage reporting both strong and weak effects to capture the full spectrum of ecological responses.

4.1.14 Identification of indicator species for MHWs

We recommend supporting research to identify and validate indicator species for monitoring the effects of marine heatwaves (MHWs), particularly in sensitive regions such as the Arctic. This includes investigating species such as non-indigenous organisms with wide temperature tolerances. Empirical studies, including those by Gubanov et al., (2022) in the Black Sea, provide evidence that such indicators can serve as early-warning proxies for detecting environmental stress, thus facilitating timely management interventions. Policies should integrate these research findings into marine management guidelines and encourage further interdisciplinary research to validate these indicators across diverse marine environments.

4.2 Summary of policy recommendations

In summary, striving to implement these policy recommendations will significantly contribute to the European Green Deal by promoting climate resilience, protecting marine biodiversity, and promoting the sustainable use of ocean resources. Enhanced ocean observing and monitoring systems will support the development of adaptive management strategies that address both global and local environmental challenges, thus reinforcing the ocean–climate–biodiversity nexus. This integrated approach not only aligns with the European environmental and sustainability goals but also creates socio-economic benefits by empowering coastal communities, stimulating innovation in ocean technologies, and preserving the marine ecosystems.

The development of an interdisciplinary ocean observing system would benefit from interdisciplinary collaborations and coordination of ongoing activities in alignment with regional and global efforts (e.g., All Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance (AAORIA), GOOS Biology & ecosystem Panel (2022), the Marine Biodiversity Observation Network (MBON)). Enhancing coordination among national and international observation networks, adopting best practices, fostering the implementation of EOVs, standardising data formats, promoting interoperability and open access publication, and promoting knowledge sharing will minimize redundancy, boost efficiency and improve more effective ocean observation.

5. The way forward

The challenges facing our ocean, from the increasing frequency of MHWs to the underrepresentation of biodiversity in observation systems, demand a shift in how we design, operate, and apply ocean monitoring frameworks. The work of BioEcoOcean and ObsSea4Clim marks an important step towards this transformation. Through joint efforts and the forthcoming Blueprint for Integrated Ocean Science, we are building the tools and relationships needed to turn fragmented data into actionable knowledge. A critical component of this shift will be the systematic implementation and operationalisation of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), which offer a standardised framework for observing the ocean system across physical, biogeochemical, and biology & ecosystem domains. Strengthening EOv-based observations and enhance their integration will help close persistent knowledge gaps and provide the foundation for more effective marine conservation and climate mitigation strategies. Continued collaboration across disciplines, sectors, and scales will be essential. As this work progresses, it will create new pathways for more inclusive, standardised, and policy-relevant ocean observations. This is not just an opportunity; it is the call to action for securing a sustainable and climate-resilient future for our oceans and the communities that rely on them.

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